

The Effect of Online Media Literacy on Peace Education in Public Universities in Rivers State.

by

Nkeiruka Queendarline Nwaizugbu; Chioma Atuzie

Department of Curriculum Studies and Educational Technology, Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria. nkeiruka.nwaizugbu@uniport.edu.ng

Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Nigeria. chiomycharles@gmail.com .

Abstract

The curriculum for peace education and national development aims to equip students with the knowledge, skills and values necessary to promote social cohesion and sustainable development in their communities and beyond. It focuses on fostering a culture of peace, understanding and respect for diversity and preparing individuals to actively participate in building peaceful and inclusive societies. In higher institutions of Nigeria peace is vital to facilitate the set goals of students, their institutions and their immediate society. The purpose of this study therefore was to find out the awareness of students on online media literacy and how it affects peace education. Four research questions drawn from the research objectives guided this study. The population for this study were students from Public Universities in Rivers State and 385 students represented the sample of this study. The instrument used for data collection was a self-constructed questionnaire consisting of a 4-point Likert type rating scale which ranged from one (lowest response) to four (highest response). Data gathered was analysed using mean and standard deviation. Findings from this study indicated that online media literacy plays a crucial role in the promotion of peace education in the digital age, social media platforms play a prominent role in disseminating misinformation and biased content among students and a relationship exist between media literacy and peace promotion in Public Universities. Based on the findings some recommendations were also made to guide appropriate stakeholders on the proactive steps to take.

Keywords: Media literacy; online media; peace education; social media ; viral news.

Introduction

The curriculum for peace education and national development is a cornerstone of education systems worldwide, designed to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and values essential for promoting social cohesion and sustainable development in their communities and beyond. At its core, peace education strives to cultivate a culture of peace, foster understanding and respect for diversity, and prepare individuals to actively engage in building peaceful and inclusive societies. This mission is particularly crucial within the higher education landscape of Nigeria, where the pursuit of peace is intricately linked to achieving the goals of students, educational institutions, and broader society. In today's digital age, online media literacy has emerged as a critical facet of education. It empowers individuals to engage with information and media in a discerning and informed manner, which is essential for responsible citizenship and constructive participation in societal development. To provide a solid foundation for this investigation, we will review relevant literature that sheds light on the interconnectedness of online media literacy, education, and peace. UNICEF defines Peace education as the process of promoting the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to bring about behaviour changes that will enable children, youth and adults to prevent conflict and violence, both overt and structural; to resolve conflict peacefully; and to create the conditions conducive to peace, whether at an intrapersonal, interpersonal, intergroup, national or international level.(Fountains, 1999).

According to Akudolu as cited by Olowo 2016, the overriding goal of Peace Education in formal, non-formal education is to develop in the learner the disposition and confidence as agents of peace who can live in harmony with oneself, others and the natural environment as well as promote peace, human rights and democracy in the society. Peace education certainly promotes knowledge , skills and attitudes that help people to prevent conflict, resolve conflicts peacefully or create social conditions conducive to peace, stability and harmony. Non-violence and core values of social justice are both central to peace education. (Isam, 2022). Peace education must address the prevention and resolution of all forms of conflict and violence, whether overt or structural, from the interpersonal level to the societal and global level. (Fountain, 1999). Even without structured and facilitated conversations, higher education provides countless informal opportunities for students to question the values and practices of their homes and families and begin to make their own decisions as adults. Coupled with an environment of study, reflection and activism, university is a place where many begin to construct a separate identity for themselves. As such, it presents a vital opportunity to address the transformation of conflict. (Millican, et al, 2021). Teaching peace education in schools will present to the learners the negative effects of violence to persons and state and direct their mind to how to use a powerful argument and civilized diplomacy to achieve lasting peace that will usher in a political stability, national integration and economic development. (Ikwumelu et al, 2014). Online media literacy encompasses the ability to critically analyse, evaluate, and create media content in digital formats.

Received: 12 August 2024

Revised: 22 August 2024

Accepted: 6 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13711317](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13711317)

It equips individuals with the skills to navigate the vast landscape of online information, identify misinformation, and engage in digital communication responsibly. As the digital realm continues to evolve, the importance of online media literacy in education becomes increasingly evident.

One of the central theoretical frameworks that was aptly applied to this study is the Media Effects Theory. This theory has been fundamental in understanding how media exposure can shape individuals' attitudes, beliefs, behaviours and perceptions. Media Effects Theory posits that the media, including online media, can exert influence on its audience, leading to changes in knowledge, attitudes and behaviours (Perse and Lambe, 2016). In the context of this study, the Media Effect Theory offers valuable insights into how online media literacy may influence the students' perception and engagement with peace education.

The Media Effect Theory suggests that individuals are exposed to various messages through media, which can influence their knowledge acquisition. In the case of online media literacy students who possess strong skills in critically assessing online content may be better equipped to access accurate and reliable information related to peace education (Vorderer et al., 2006). This, in turn, can enhance their knowledge base. The Media Effect Theory also addresses how media exposure can shape attitudes. In the context of peace education, students who engage with online media and are media-literate may be more inclined to form positive attitudes towards peace and conflict resolution. They may be better equipped to recognize and critically evaluate messages promoting peaceful coexistence (Huesmann, 2018). Finally, the theory explores how media exposure can lead to behavioural changes. Here, online media literacy could empower students to actively engage in peace -building activities, dialogue and conflict resolution within their university communities and beyond (Valkenburg and Peter, 2013). The application of Media Effect Theory to the study “ The Effect of Online Media Literacy on Peace Education in Public Universities in Rivers State” provided a comprehensive lens through which to understand how students' exposure to online media and their level of online media literacy may influence their engagement with peace education. It underscores the importance of media literacy in equipping students to navigate online information critically and constructively contribute to peace-building efforts within their communities.

The literature on online media literacy emphasises its role in enhancing traditional education. Many educational institutions have adopted a cross-disciplinary approach, integrating digital literacy skills into existing curricula. For instance, students in history classes may learn to critically analyse online historical sources(Friesem and Ariel, 2019). Online media education affords consumers of information the depth to read in between the lines and make informed judgements and evaluation of whatever they read or listen to online. (Bamgbose, 2023). Online media literacy enhances formal education by making students more active, critical learners and creators of media. The intersection of online media literacy and peace education is of growing

significance. In an era where misinformation and digital echo chambers can perpetuate conflicts and misunderstandings, media literacy skills are essential for navigating the digital landscape (Livingstone & Bulger, 2013). Beyond that, online media can be a powerful tool for promoting peace, facilitating cross-cultural dialogue, and disseminating conflict resolution resources (Mullen & Paterson, 2011). Peace Education can be done by educating the public through the use of information media that are now rife with digital media or social media. (Tachoh, 2020). According to Naseem, Arshad-Ayaz & Doyle (2017), spaces like the blogosphere empower people to take control of conversations that impact and involve them, these spaces help transform individual voices into booming public ones.

Findings from a study by Adekunmisi, et al 2022 that assessed the media literacy skills level of undergraduates in Ogun State, Nigeria, revealed that 69.0% (520) undergraduates possessed high media literacy skills, 28.5% (215) possessed moderate media literacy skills, while 2.5% (19) possessed low media literacy skills. This indicated possession of high media literacy skills among undergraduates. A study by Nasir & Ciroma (2023), who sought to determine if students at Colleges of Education in Northern Nigeria had developed the psychomotor skills required to recognize fake news (i.e., picture news, video news, and written social media/blog/website news), found that Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) students in northern colleges lack psychomotor capability to verify fake news either through a manual or automatic method. Findings from Ukam et al, 2020 in their study that examined the influence of media literacy on the health outcome of youths revealed that media literacy has a great impact on the health outcome of youths. According to the results of a research by Dolanbay, (2022) that sought to improve the media literacy awareness of university students, the media literacy awareness of the students used for the research, which was weak at the beginning, increased by strengthening after an eight-week media literacy training. Students gained an important awareness about criticising the media and questioning the media, and production. Jones & Mitchell (2016) in their research on trends in youth internet victimisation, analysed data from three youth internet safety surveys conducted between 2000 and 2010. The study reveals patterns in how online risks have evolved and how youth awareness and coping strategies have developed over time. Their work highlights the importance of ongoing media literacy education to help students navigate and mitigate online risks effectively. Culver and Redmond (2019) whose research explored how media literacy can contribute to a culture of peace by influencing students' media consumption and production habits, findings showed that students with high levels of media literacy are more likely to engage with media content that aligns with peace-oriented values.

The digital age has brought about a proliferation of information sources, making it increasingly challenging to discern reliable information from misinformation and disinformation. Public universities in Rivers State are not immune to this problem, as students and faculty encounter a constant stream of unverified and potentially biased content online. The spread of

Received: 12 August 2024

Revised: 22 August 2024

Accepted: 6 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13711317>

false information can undermine the foundation of peace education by promoting ignorance, mistrust, and hostility among students, faculty, and the wider community. Social media platforms and online communities have provided a space for the amplification of divisive narratives and hate speech. This phenomenon poses a significant threat to peace education in public universities, as it can foster a hostile and polarised environment that hinders constructive dialogue and collaboration. Furthermore, while the importance of online media literacy is widely acknowledged, there is a lack of formalised programs and curricula dedicated to equipping students with the necessary skills to navigate the digital information landscape responsibly. Public universities in Rivers State may not have fully integrated online media literacy education into their academic offerings, potentially leaving students ill-prepared to critically evaluate online content. In a study by Scharrer and Ramasubramanian (2015), students expressed the belief that online media literacy contributes to peace education by enhancing their ability to critically evaluate sources and understand diverse perspectives. The study found that students who engage in media literacy programs are more likely to question stereotypes and biases presented in online content, which in turn fosters a culture of peace and understanding. Guess, Nagler, and Tucker (2019) investigated the extent to which fake news is shared on Facebook and identified the demographic factors associated with the spread of misinformation. This study indicates that students with lower digital literacy may be more likely to share misinformation on social media. According to them, enhancing digital literacy among students is crucial to countering the spread of biased content on social media.

The impact of online media literacy on peace education in public universities is a subject that warrants thorough investigation. While literature recognizes the importance of online media literacy and peace education independently, there is a research gap concerning their interconnectedness, especially in the context of Nigerian public universities. This study aimed to address this gap by investigating students' awareness of online media literacy and its potential impact on their engagement with peace education initiatives. The study explores how students' ability to distinguish credible sources affects their understanding of peacebuilding, conflict resolution, and social harmony. Additionally, it will assess whether there is a correlation between high levels of online media literacy and the promotion of tolerance, empathy, and inclusivity within university communities.

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to ascertain the awareness of students in public universities in Rivers State regarding the importance of online media literacy and peace education. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the extent of awareness among students in public universities in Rivers State regarding online media literacy and its significance.
2. Explore students' perceptions of the importance of online media literacy in fostering peace education and its relevance in the digital age.
3. Investigate the extent social media platforms are sources of students' acceptance of misinformation and biased content.
4. Assess whether there is a relationship between high levels of online media literacy and the promotion of peace in Public Universities?

Research Questions

1. To what extent are students in Public Universities in Rivers State aware of the significance of online media literacy in today's digital age?
2. How do students' perceive the importance of online media literacy in fostering peace education and its relevance in the digital age?
3. To what extent are social media platforms sources of students' misinformation and biased content?
4. What is the relationship between high media literacy rate and the promotion of peace in Public Universities?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey design to explore the awareness of students in public universities in Rivers State regarding the importance of online media literacy and peace education. Nwankwo, (2013) noted that descriptive survey study is that in which the researcher collects data from a large sample drawn from given population and describes certain features of the sample as they are at the time of the study and which are of interest to the researcher, however, without manipulating any independent variables of the study. The target population of this study consisted of 88,000 students of Public Universities in River State and 385 students which was obtained by using the Krejci and Morgan Sample Size Determination Table representing the sample of the study. The instrument that was used for data collection was a questionnaire with 20 items titled "Evaluating Awareness Levels: Online Media Literacy and Peace Education in Rivers State Public Universities" The instrument comprises of a 4-point likert scale type rating scale which ranged

Received: 12 August 2024

Revised: 22 August 2024

Accepted: 6 September 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13711317](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13711317)

from one (lowest response) to four (highest response). The method of data analysis used for this study was mean and standard deviation. A standard reference mean of 2.50 was adopted for the purpose of determining the degree of awareness of students in public universities in Rivers State regarding the importance of online media literacy and peace education.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent are students in Public Universities in Rivers State aware of the significance of online media literacy in today's digital age?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent Students in Public Universities in Rivers State are aware of the Significance of Online Media Literacy in Today's Digital Age.

S/ N	ITEMS	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
1	I believe that online media literacy is crucial in today's digital age."	3.24	3.86	High
2	I actively seek to improve my online media literacy skills (e.g., fact-checking, evaluating sources).	2.39	2.09	Low
3	It is important to have the ability to differentiate between reliable and unreliable online information.	3.69	3.23	High
4	Lacking the ability to use digital technologies means that there are many things you simply cannot do or access.	3.15	2.79	High
5.	Becoming digitally literate and understanding good online safety practices can help to increase your safety.	3.65	3.19	High

Table 1 above shows the

responses of students on the extent to which they are aware of the importance of online literacy in today's digital age. Item 1 which has a mean score of 3.24 indicates that to a high extent students believe that online media literacy is crucial in today's digital age. 3, 4 and 5 above have a mean score above 2.5 which was adopted for the purpose of determining the degree of awareness of students in public universities in Rivers State regarding the importance of online media literacy and peace education. But clearly item 3 has a mean score below 2.5. This indicates that although students acknowledge the importance of online media literacy, to a high extent they do not have the ability to differentiate between reliable and unreliable online information.

Research Question 2: How relevant is online media literacy in the context of peace education in the digital age?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of how Students Perceive the Importance of Online Media Literacy in Fostering Peace Education and its Relevance in the Digital Age.

S/ N	ITEMS	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
6	Online media literacy plays a crucial role in promoting peace and tolerance in society.	2.45	2.17	Low
7	Misinformation and biased content online can contribute to conflicts in society.	2.63	2.68	High
8	Online media literacy should be integrated into peace education programs.	3.07	2.72	High
9	Media literacy helps people make informed choices about how they participate in peace building and equality.	2.86	2.60	High
10	Media literacy helps people make informed choices about how they participate in freedom of expression and dialogue.	3.41	3.05	High

Table 2 above represents the responses of students to how relevant online media literacy is in the context of peace education in the digital age. All the items on Table 2 have a mean score above 2.5 which indicate that students in Public Universities in Rivers State acknowledge that online media literacy is relevant in the framework of peace education in today’s world.

Research Question 3: To what extent are social media platforms sources of students’ misinformation and biased content?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Extent to which Social Media Platforms are Sources of Students’ Misinformation and Biassed Content

S/ N	ITEMS	$\bar{x}$	SD	Remarks
11	Social media platforms are mostly the first source of news for me	3.29	2.90	High
12	I often encounter misinformation and biased content on social media platforms.	3.4	2.96	High
13	I am concerned about the impact of misinformation and biased content on my attitudes and beliefs.	2.29	1.98	Low
14	Social media platforms have a significant influence on shaping my attitudes toward information.	3.05	2.73	High
15	Watching a video on social media makes you believe the information easily.	2.65	2.34	High

Table 3 above shows the mean and standard deviation responses of students to the extent to which social media platforms are sources of misinformation and biased content. Items 11, 12, 14 and 15 have mean scores above 2.5 and item 13 has a mean score below 2.5. This indicates that even as students are of the opinion that social media platforms are the main sources of misinformation and biased content, the extent to which they are concerned about the impact of misinformation and biased content on their attitudes and beliefs is low.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between high media literacy rate and the promotion of peace in Public Universities?

Table 4: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Relationship between High Media Literacy Rate and the Promotion of Peace in Public Universities?

S/N	ITEMS	$\bar{x}$	SD
16	Media literacy can contribute to the promotion of peace and tolerance in society.	2.67	2.38
17	Media literacy can serve as an effective and active agent of peace education in Public Universities.	3.24	2.87
18	I believe that effective media literacy can help eradicate ethnic and religious conflicts in society.	2.87	2.53
19	The promotion of peace education can be achieved by focusing on media literacy of students	2.70	2.41
20	When the media literacy rate is high there will also be a high level of peace in society.	2.62	2.35

Table 4 above shows that mean ratings of 2.67, 3.24, 2.87, 2.70 and 2.62 respectively are above the standard reference mean of 2.50. This suggests that, on average, students perceived a strong connection between media literacy and the promotion of peace.

Discussion of Findings

The results from Table 1 which addressed research question one shows that there is a strong consensus among students that online media literacy is of paramount importance in navigating the digital age effectively underscores the growing awareness among students about the significance of digital literacy. This affirms the findings of Jones & Mitchell (2016) that reveals patterns in how online risks have evolved and how youth awareness and coping strategies have developed over time. This finding has profound implications for educational institutions, highlighting the urgent need to incorporate digital literacy programs into curricula.

Findings from Table 2 indicate that students in Public Universities in Rivers State acknowledge that online media literacy is relevant in the framework of peace education in today's world. This agrees with Scharrer and Ramasubramanian (2015) who posited that students who engage in media literacy programs are more likely to question stereotypes and biases presented in online content, which in turn fosters a culture of peace and understanding. This implies that integrating online media literacy within peace education curricula can enhance students' capacity to engage in constructive dialogues, mediate conflicts, and promote peaceful coexistence.

Findings obtained from research question three shows that social media platforms play a prominent role in disseminating misinformation and biased content among students. This is in line with Guess, Nagler, and Tucker (2019) that indicates that students with lower digital literacy

may be more prone to sharing misinformation. This finding highlights the need for digital media literacy programs that focus on critical thinking and fact-checking skills.

Findings from research question four suggests that, on average, students perceived a strong connection between media literacy and the promotion of peace. This affirms the findings from Culver and Redmond (2019) that found a strong correlation between students' media literacy levels and their understanding of media's role in either perpetuating or mitigating conflict. The revelation that students generally hold positive views about the relationship between media literacy and peace promotion in Public Universities is a testament to the potential of media literacy education.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data and findings made, the following conclusions were drawn;

1. There is a strong consensus among students that online media literacy is of paramount importance in navigating the digital age effectively.
2. There is a strong consensus among students that online media literacy plays a crucial role in the promotion of peace education in the digital age.
3. The majority of students believe that social media platforms play a prominent role in disseminating misinformation and biased content among students.
4. Students generally hold positive views about the relationship between media literacy and peace promotion in Public Universities.

The conclusions drawn from this study underscore the critical role of online media literacy, its impact on peace education, the challenge of misinformation, and the potential of media literacy for peace promotion in the digital age. Educational institutions, particularly Public Universities, must recognize these implications and respond by integrating comprehensive media literacy programs into their educational offerings. By doing so, they can empower students to navigate the digital landscape responsibly, contribute to peacebuilding efforts, and counter the spread of misinformation, ultimately fostering a more informed and harmonious society.

Recommendations

1. Public Universities should prioritise equipping students with the skills and knowledge necessary to critically assess online information, fostering responsible digital citizenship.
2. Educational institutions should consider the development of interdisciplinary programs that combine media literacy and peace studies to address contemporary challenges effectively.

3. Universities should collaborate with students to develop strategies for promoting media literacy and digital discernment. Additionally, they should encourage responsible social media usage and provide resources to identify and combat misinformation.
4. Public Universities should initiate media literacy initiatives that emphasise the role of informed communication in peacebuilding. These programs can empower students to utilise media as a tool for promoting tolerance, understanding, and conflict resolution both within and beyond academic settings.

References

- Adekunmisi, S. R., Oyewusi, F. O., & Aramide, K. A. (2022). Assessment of media literacy skills of undergraduates in universities in ogun state, nigeria. *Mousaion: South African Journal of Information Studies*, 40(2), <https://doi.org/10.25159/2663-659X/9811>
- Buckingham, D. (2003). Chapter Three of Media Education: Literacy, Learning and Contemporary Culture.
- Culver, S., & Redmond, T. (2019). Media literacy and its role in promoting a culture of peace. *Media Education Research Journal*, 9(2), 24-35.
- Fountain, S. (1999). Peace education in UNICEF. *United Nations Children's Fund Programme Publications 3 UN Plaza New York, NY 10017 USA*
- Galtung, J. (1990). Cultural violence. *Journal of Peace Research*, 27(3), 291-305.
- Guess, A., Nagler, J., & Tucker, J. (2019). Less than you think: Prevalence and predictors of fake news dissemination on Facebook. *Science Advances*, 5(1), eaau4586.
- Ikwumelu, S. N, Oyibe, O.A & Eluu P. E. (2014). Peace education: An instrument for enhancing national security in Nigeria. *World Educators Forum*. 4, 303-313.
- Jones, L. M., & Mitchell, K. J. (2016). Trends in youth internet victimization: Findings from three youth internet safety surveys 2000-2010. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 50(2), 179-186.
- Livingstone, S., & Bulger, M. (2013). A global research agenda for children's rights in the digital age. *Journal of Children and Media*, 7(4), 1-17.
- Mullen, B., & Paterson, R. (2011). The potential of new media in conflict prevention and management. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 6(1), 51-65.

Naseem, M. A., Arshad-Ayaz, A., & Doyle, S. (2017). Social media as space for peace education: Conceptual contours and evidence from the Muslim world. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 12(1), 95–109. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745499917696422>

Nasir, M. J. & Ciroma, A. (2023). Impact of Media and Information Literacy in Nigerian Colleges of Education Curriculum: A Case of Detecting Fake News. *American Journal of Communication*, 5(1), 28 - 37. <https://doi.org/10.47672/ajc.1385>

Olowo, O.O. (2016). 9 Effects of integrating peace education in the Nigeria education system. *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1735 ISSN 2222-288X (Online) 7 (18)

Salomon, G. (2002). Studying the impact of technology on teaching and learning: A response to the review of contemporary research on technology and education published by the American Educational Research Association. *Contemporary Issues in Technology and Teacher Education*, 2(2), 202-210.

Scharrer, E., & Ramasubramanian, S. (2015). Intervening in the media's influence on stereotypes of race and ethnicity: The role of media literacy education. *Journal of Social Issues*, 71(1), 171-185.

Tacoh, Y.T.B (2020). Peace education through digital literacy on social media (Analysis of the ability of facilitators in Poso District Women's School of Peace). *European Union Digital Library* <http://dx.doi.org/10.4108/eai.26-11-2019.2295211>

Ukam, I. N., & Ukam, S. (2020). Influence of digital media literacy on health outcome of youths: A call for increased media education. *Journal of Advanced Mass Communication and Journalism* 1(1): 16-22